

Improving English Language through Listening Podcast

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Abstract

The use of podcasts is very helpful for creating activities in the classroom and students seemed to be very motivated and interested in listening and to listen and practice speaking. The Students were able to take specific information from the podcasts and work in groups to use the information. Podcasts present a variety of interesting topics that can broaden that can broaden students' horizons. By using instructional technology technology, such as podcasts, teachers can also and develop their skills in using the technology. with the technology. This is evident with their English intonation production, students tend to raise the pitch at the end of a declarative sentence. declarative sentences, which automatically changes the mood of the sentence into an integrative sentences. In addition, this study also shows that English learners have inadequate knowledge of suprasegmental features in English, especially intonation. This This shows that teaching English, especially pronunciation, can be very difficult because students perceive intonation as a students' perception of intonation in relation to native speakers' use of English intonation. By using podcasts, in addition to practicing English, students can also be entertained and increase their enthusiasm for learning. Therefore, podcasts can be considered as an important medium in English language teaching.

Keywords: *English Language, Listening, Podcast*

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INTRODUCTION

In this study, students are expected to improve their English language skills using podcast media. Students only need to familiarize themselves with listening to podcasts so that students will train their hearing with English conversations and gain new vocabulary. Students can adjust the level of English they have to the quality of the podcast they want to hear, therefore students can easily learn to improve their listening skills by using podcast media.

In reality, students have little difficulty in understanding what they hear from the story or conversation on the podcast. The difficulty they experience in understanding conversations in podcasts may be due to the lack of vocabulary possessed by students, and the speed of the speakers contained in the podcast so that students have difficulty in capturing every sentence in the conversation in the podcast. Therefore, students must be able to choose the level of podcast according to their abilities.

In listening to podcasts there are several things that can be practiced by listening to audio podcasts. Apart from just being able to be listened to, podcasts also provide several things especially for students. Therefore, the author will answer and explain a question: podcast improve language skill?

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

According to Ramli (2018), Influences Of using podcast in English language skills such as Listening and speaking contribute a lot to give some Improvements both for the teachers and the students. podcast provides: Learning styles, ways to Practice listening, increase vocabulary , Grammatical sentence, intonation, and Pronunciation.

1. Learning styles

Learning styles are regarded as one of keys of students achieving their academic goals. Styles in general refers to consistent rather and rather enduring Tendencies or preferences within an Individual, in addition, it connects to General characteristics of intellectual Functioning (and personality type, as Well) that pertain to someone as an Individual, and that differentiate Someone from someone else (Brown,2010). Learning style can also mean Certain pattern of behaviour and or Performance in which the individual Approaches a learning experience, a Way in which the individual

takes in new Information and develop new skills (Renou, 2009), and the process by Which the individual retain new Information or skills; it can also be the Preferences of an individual to perceive And process information in particular Way or combination of ways.

Research on learning styles has been carried out by several Researchers; first, Widharyanto & Binawan (2020) their research explains that of the five Ethnic groups, it was found that they were dominant in aural, kinesthetic, and various Learning styles in bimodal and trimodal forms. Second, Baihaqi et al., (2020) his research Revealed that students' confidence in learning pronunciation can be achieved and increased Through learning styles by practicing listening to songs, watching, and reading books in English. Third, Maryono & Lengkanawati (2022) the result of this research is the learning process from a distance can also be useful for teachers and students EFL to find out student Learning styles during learning. Fourth, Suparman's result showed that cognitive learning Styles are very influential in the process of teaching vocabulary, so cognitive learning styles Influence students' reading comprehension contextually.

Student involvement in learning a lesson is very effective so it must focus On developing student learning that involves educational institutions (Marcy, 2001). In Addition, students can change their learning habits by following their willingness to learn so That they can help improve student academic achievement (Sinha et al., 2013; Urval et al., 2014). Faisal (2019) states individual characteristics and learning style preferences greatly Influence students' language achievement.

2. Ways to Practise listening

According to Galina Kavaliauskienė, Lilija Anusienė (2009) Language practitioners are well aware that listening activity in English for Specific Purposes Is an active and demanding process of selecting And interpreting information from auditory And visual clues In listening, there are several major steps which Include determining a reason for listening, predicting information, attempting to organize information, assigning a meaning to the message, And transferring information from short-term Memory to long-term memory.

An important feature of listening process is That much of processing of incoming information takes place during the pauses in speech. Pauses in natural speech allow students to gain Processing time. Moreover, much of comprehension involves drawing inferences. A characteristic feature of listening is a creation of Mental messages which are stored by learners. This phenomenon is known as a false recognition memory (Rivers 1992).

Podcasts are part of novel online learning And can serve a number of purposes: to enhance The range and register of English language Listening practice material available for the Students to use in a variety of ways; to provide Increased connectivity between different elements of the course; to increase the scope for Discussion activity. The podcasts online have Given the language teacher a wealth of materials for teaching listening skills. P. Constantine (2007) examines the subject of podcasts on Several levels and deals with the questions of The podcast advantages, selection of the most Beneficial podcasts, and discusses how to maximize learning from podcasts.

Listening to podcasts had to serve a number Of learning goals: first, to enhance the range and Register of English language listening practice Material available for the students to use in a Variety of ways; second, to provide increased Connectivity between different elements of the Course; third, to increase the scope for discussion activity in the classroom in pairs after students have shared their listening experiences. An innovative way of practicing listening Skills is podcasting which enables learners to Conduct the activity at their own pace and at the Convenient time. Real life listening, e.g. socializing with the native speakers of English, is not Feasible on the daily basis in this country, but It is highly appreciated by learners at tertiary Level.

There are some rationales why podcast can be used in order to improve the students' English listening and speaking performance. The reason of why podcast could help Indonesian students enhance their listening and speaking skill is the fact that podcast enables students to be exposed to authentic language use of English. This is, particularly, because the materials in podcast cover a wide range of topics with real life speech and are generally prepared by native speakers (Thorne & Payne, 2005; Stanley, 2005; Rosell-Aguilar, 2007; Hasan & Hoon, 2013). For example, from the authentic podcast materials, the students can listen to everyday conversations in the real life situation, familiarise themselves with English pronunciation and practice their listening as well as speaking skill.

The exposure to the authentic materials is unquestionably important to provide a meaningful language learning experience (Brown, 2007), especially in Indonesia, where the students have limited experience in real life communication outside the classroom (Hapsari & Ratri, 2014). This meaningful learning experience will further increase their engagement and motivation to learn English and improve their listening and speaking performance, as explained by O'Bryan and Hegelheimer (2007).

3. Increase vocabulary

Vocabulary is an element of language skills that helps people to express Ideas or a key determinant for linking the four skills in English such as; listening, Speaking, writing or reading (receptive and productive skills), having less Vocabulary will effect on missing the pieces of information . (Zhang & Annual, 2008) Students with low vocabulary in certain languages will lose information that Can affect their understanding and ability when using the language as a means of Gaining new knowledge.

In learning languages, vocabulary is the main foundation for the creation of Understanding, fluency, and achievement (Howard et al., 2014). In addition to Having good vocabulary mastery students also need to understand their use Accurately and contextually through listening or applying it in various ways, (Sardi Et al., 2015). This will be difficult to achieve if we only rely on school environment, They need guidance or direction to continue learning everywhere. For this reason, a Media that is able to make students actively to study wherever and whenever is Needed. Besides being able to be accessed anytime and anywhere, of course the Media must be fun, can be used while relaxing, lying down, in a bus or train.

Nozari & Siamian (2015) educating using software Is able to provide rich resources as well as can be an opportunity for growth in Learning, and creating a collaborative environment that allows students and Teachers to find relevant resources, and to learn various things. Similarly, there Was a significant increase in learning performance integrated with podcasting (Gholami & Mohammadi, 2015).using podcasts will make Students not only focus on social media and online games, but students can also Use their time to listen to information and aquire more vocabulary from podcast Broadcasts (Smart Smartphone users) (ibnu, yusdayanti, Rosita, 2020)

4. Gramatical sentence

Grammar can be difficult to learn. It can be challenging for some pupils to put it Into practice in spoken and written language. It takes place in a classroom. It is referred To as explicit learning. The majority, however, believe that using grammatical rules in Both written and verbal communication is acceptable. Students who speak English as Their first language encounter it. Implicit learning is it. Acquisition of the phenomenon of explicit grammar acquisition takes a lot of work. Furthermore, acquiring grammar Implicitly occurs unconsciously. The grammatical rule is unknown to the students. The Teacher could use noticing to transition the children from explicit to implicit learning. It Is a method of internalizing the norm by concentrating on the shape and significance of The linguistic structure (Suseno, 2021).

According to Edy Suseno (2023) People use the device to communicate with other users and to access a wealth of Information. It is a device that offers opportunities for various uses, including business, Education, and many other things. A lot of pupils struggle to master proper grammar And pronunciation. The applications students can use to improve their speaking and Grammatical skills are podcasts. By looking for them on their devices, the students can Find them. Using podcast content enhances learning grammar and pronunciation. The frequency of classroom participation and task completion affect the success of such a method's adoption (Alfino et al., 2019). The two improvements enable the students to learn more naturally in structure and pronunciation by enhancing their inputs.

The study of grammar based on created podcasts contributes to the development of grammatical skills and improves the quality Of teaching and learning, as well as the active dissemination of experiences (Chaikovska, 2020). They promote creativity and Supports learner autonomy (Thompson, 2007). They had a positive impact on students' engagement and performance in a Beginning level Japanese language course (Takeda, 2013) and a positive effect on learning and motivation of at-risk high school Students (Checho, 2007).

5. Intonation

Intonation thus involves, besides other acoustic features, meaningful pitch in several Domains. Halliday (1967) calls the primary domains tone, tonality, and tonicity. Tone (elsewhere and

more commonly called tone) is intonation to communicate meaning at the end of a sentence. Thus the choice of rising versus falling in the utterance *He's ready* is an example of a tone choice. Tonality divides spoken phrases, as in the sentence *If you leave now, don't come back*. Third, tonicity is the use of pitch to single out a word or syllable as informationally prominent, as in *HE'S ready* versus *He's READY*. It also may include significant uses of pitch range called KEY (Brazil, 1997).

A mistaken belief is that intonation reinforces grammatical meaning. While intonation may sometimes correlate with syntax (for example, declaratives in English tend to have falling tones in most contexts), intonation is not simply a mirror of grammar. Instead, it provides an independent source of pragmatic or sociolinguistic meaning. Some research has shown that half of all polar questions (yes/no) in English can occur with rising intonation and half with falling (Thompson, 1995). Recent research on Dutch shows that phonological, syntactic and pragmatic factors all serve to distinguish rising intonation and question fall-rise intonations in read and freely spoken questions (Lickley, Schepman, & Ladd, 2005). Modern theoretical approaches to meaning do not assume a direct causal link between intonation and grammar, but the temptation to connect the two remains strong in pedagogical approaches.

Intonation refers to the use of melody and the rise and fall of the voice when speaking. Kelly (2001) has a similar statement, she describes the term of intonation as the way the voice goes up and down in pitch when we are speaking. Speakers produce melodies by changing the frequency of vibration of the vocal cords, mostly at the accented syllable. They recognize falling and rising tones of different length – long fall and short fall, long rise and short rise – and combinations of these tones (Kreidler, 2004). Meanwhile, Hart, Coiler, and Cohen (1992:02) have more technical definition about intonation; it is the assemblage of pitch variations in speech caused by the varying periodicity in the vibrations of the vocal cords.

6. pronunciation

Pronunciation skill is one of the key elements of speaking ability. Intelligible speech necessitates the accurate production of many factors, e.g., phonemes, stress, linking, rhythm, and intonation. According to Burnkart as cited on Pardede (2008, p.1) emphasized that, in addition to grammar and vocabulary, pronunciation constitutes the mechanical elements of speaking skill. Therefore, to be effective in speaking must pronounce accurately. Pronunciation is a part of speaking skill that is truly important to make the communication runs well, thus pronunciation is an important factor in language learning. According to Yuzawa (2007), "pronunciation is a basic and essential skill required for those who want to use English communicatively". Based on Yuzawa's statement, pronunciation is needed to be taught in order to help the student pronounce English correctly. Implementing digital media in the classroom is one of the ways to make the teaching-learning process to be more active and fun.

Pronunciation is a component of speaking that should be mastered by the students in learning English. Pronunciation is the way for students to produce clearer language. According to Yuzawa as cited in Ampuni (2017, p. 8) "Pronunciation is a fundamental and necessary skill needed for those who need to communicatively use English". It deals with the phonological cycle that refers to the grammar portion made up of elements and values that decide the variability and pattern of sounds in the language. There are two features of pronunciation; segmental and suprasegmental.

Communication in spoken English is organized by suprasegmental features. These suprasegmental features are similar to musical signals. The reason is that for the purposes of teaching pronunciation, the teacher needs to understand these musical signals work. Kelly (2001:3) states that suprasegmental features, as the name implies, are features of speech which generally apply to groups of segments, or phonemes. The features which are important in spoken English are stress, intonation, and how sounds change in connected speech which is called the rhythm. Ladefog (2010:243) adds, suprasegmental features are aspects of speech that involve more than single consonants or vowels. The principal of suprasegmental features are stress, length, tone, and intonation.

CONCLUSION

The use of podcasts is very helpful for creating activities in the classroom and students seemed to be very motivated and interested in listening and to listen and practice speaking. The students were able to take specific information from the podcasts and work in groups to use the

information. Podcasts present a variety of interesting topics that can broaden that can broaden students' horizons. By using instructional technology technology, such as podcasts, teachers can also and develop their skills in using the technology. with the technology. This is evident with their English intonation production, students tend to raise the pitch at the end of a declarative sentence. declarative sentences, which automatically changes the mood of the sentence into an integrative sentences. In addition, this study also shows that English learners have inadequate knowledge of suprasegmental features in English, especially intonation. This This shows that teaching English, especially pronunciation, can be very difficult because students perceive intonation as a students' perception of intonation in relation to native speakers' use of English intonation. By using podcasts, in addition to practicing English, students can also be entertained and increase their enthusiasm for learning. Therefore, podcasts can be considered as an important medium in English language teaching.

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